

Novel Behaviour of a Hydrazone Ligand towards Some 3d Metal Ions

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Complexes of 2,4-dihydroxyacetophenone hydrazone with trivalent iron, bivalent manganese, cobalt and nickel, and univalent copper have been synthesized. They are characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, conductance measurements and magnetic, spectral and TGA data. The ligand reduces copper(II) to copper(I) at pH 5-6. It coordinates to the metal ions through variable donor sequences, behaving as an ON donor towards manganese(II), iron(III) and nickel(II), ONN donor towards cobalt(II) and ONNO donor towards copper(I). Square planar geometry to iron(III) and nickel(II), distorted square planar to cobalt(II) and tetrahedral arrangement to manganese(II) and copper(I) are proposed.

AMONGST the azomethine derivatives of hydrazine and substituted hydrazines^{1,2}, those having $>C=NNH_2$ moiety have been comparatively less investigated in terms of their chelating ability³. Some reports show that hydrazones like $CH_3CH=NNH_2$ can reduce copper(II) to copper(I)⁴. Synthesis and characterization of 2,4-dihydroxyacetophenone hydrazone (resacetophenone hydrazone, RAH) and its metal complexes with manganese(II), iron(III), cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(I) are described in this paper.

Experimental

AnalaR grade chemicals were used. Elemental analysis was done as per standard methods. Philips conductivity bridge, model 3201 was used for conductance measurements. IR spectra were recorded in KBr pellets in the range of 4000-200 cm^{-1} using Perkin Elmer, 577 spectrophotometer and electronic (mull) spectra were recorded in the visible and ultra violet regions (700-230 nm) using Cary 17D instrument. Magnetic data were obtained at room temperature by using Faraday technique. The magnetic moment values have been corrected for diamagnetism and TIP. TGA data were obtained on a manually operated thermobalance.

Preparation of resacetophenone hydrazone (RAH) : A solution of resacetophenone (0.1 mole) in methanol (15 ml) was added to hydrazine hydrate (0.15 mole) and the contents were heated on a water bath for 30 min. Pale yellow compound (yield ~90%), which separated out on cooling, was filtered, washed with adequate amount of methanol and crystallized from methanol.

Preparation of the metal complexes : All the metal complexes were prepared following the general procedure mentioned below.

The respective metal chloride [i.e. Mn(II), Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II)], (0.01 mole) in

methanol (30 ml) was added to RAH (0.03 mole) in methanol (50 ml) and the mixture refluxed for about 1 hr. The product separated out on adjusting the pH in the range of 6-8 with alcoholic ammonia solution (1%). It was filtered hot, washed with hot methanol and dried *in vacuo*. The yields are almost quantitative for Cu(II) and Fe(III) and in the range of 60-80% for the others.

Results and Discussion

The results of elemental analysis reveal the following compositions for RAH and its metal complexes : $C_8H_{10}O_2N_2$, $MnC_{16}H_{18}O_4N_4$, $FeC_{16}H_{18}O_4N_4Cl$, $Co_2C_{16}H_{22}O_6N_4Cl_2$, $NiC_{16}H_{18}O_4N_4$ and $CuC_8H_8O_2N_2$. The complexes are insoluble in common polar and non-polar solvents but soluble in DMSO, DMF and aqueous alkali. Conductance measurements in 1×10^{-3} M DMSO solutions indicate that Fe(III) and Co(II) complexes are 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 electrolytes, respectively, while the others are non-electrolytes.

Magnetic moments and electronic spectra : Mn(II), Fe(III) and Co(II) complexes show paramagnetism with magnetic moments of 5.7, 3.6 and 2.0 B.M., respectively, while Ni(II) and copper complexes are diamagnetic.

The electronic spectral bands (ν_{max} in cm^{-1}) observed in case of Mn(II) complex in the regions 22725-20500, 26000-24000 and 27775 have been attributed to the transitions from 6S ground state to the components of 4G , 4P and 4D and 4F terms respectively⁵, in agreement with tetrahedral arrangement. Fe(III) complex with quartet ground state shows medium intensity bands at 21000, 24000, 33000 and 38000 which may be due to the overlap of the weak d-d transitions and charge transfer transitions. Based on the magnetic data square planar geometry has been proposed to this complex⁶. Co(II) ion with doublet ground state can have either

low-spin octahedral or square planar arrangement. The analytical and electronic spectral data of this complex suggest square planar arrangement subjected to some distortion. The visible band at 20500 is assigned to ${}^2A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{1g}$ transition⁶, consistent with distorted square planar geometry.

Diamagnetism and electronic spectral bands at 15625 and 20000 assignable to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ transitions characterize square planar arrangement for Ni(II) complex⁷. The diamagnetic behaviour of copper complex is a clear evidence of the reduction of Cu(II) to Cu(I). This type of reducing behaviour has been reported earlier for a few hydrazine derivatives⁸. The preferred configuration of Cu(I) is designated as tetrahedral⁶. The intense band at 20000 can be assigned to charge transfer⁹.

Infrared spectra : The ir assignments have been made with the help of standard text books^{10,11}. The ir spectrum of RAH shows two sharp peaks at 3360 and 3270 cm^{-1} , assignable to antisymmetric and symmetric stretching of $-\text{NH}_2$ group, respectively. A broad band in the 3200-2900 cm^{-1} region is due to two phenolic hydroxyls involved in intra and inter molecular hydrogen bonding. A strong, broad band observed at 1615 cm^{-1} is assumed to be a combination of C=N stretching, $-\text{NH}_2$ bending and ring skeletal vibrations. Medium bands observed at 1400 and 1360 cm^{-1} are attributed to $-\text{OH}$ deformation of phenolic groups at positions 2 and 4, respectively. The peaks at 1220 and 1180 cm^{-1} are ascribable to phenolic C-O stretching at positions 2 and 4, respectively. Another medium band at 730 cm^{-1} is attributed to $-\text{NH}_2$ wagging.

Significant structural changes have taken place in RAH on complex formation with metal ions. A strong band at 3550 cm^{-1} assignable to free $-\text{OH}$ stretching appears in the spectra of Mn(II), Fe(III) and Ni(II) complexes. This is possibly due to $-\text{OH}$ at position 4. The persistence of bands at 1360 and 1180 cm^{-1} in these complexes due to $-\text{OH}$ deformation and C-O stretch, respectively, further confirm the presence of free $-\text{OH}$ at position 4. The OH band (position 4) in copper complex appears relatively downward at 3440 cm^{-1} indicating its involvement in coordination without deprotonation¹². In case of Co(II) complex, a broad trough in the range of 3600-2800 cm^{-1} shows the presence of coordinated water. This is confirmed by the appearance of a medium peak at 820 cm^{-1} which is characteristic of coordinated water molecule¹³. The absence of $-\text{OH}$ deformation band at 1400 cm^{-1} in all the spectra of the complexes indicates the deprotonation of $-\text{OH}$ at position 2 and the upward shift of the corresponding C-O stretch from 1220 to 1240 cm^{-1} confirm the participation of the oxygen in coordination. The persistence of $-\text{NH}_{2\text{sym}}$ stretch at 3270 cm^{-1} and the blue shift of $-\text{NH}_{2\text{asym}}$

stretch in the spectra of all the complexes except those of Co(II) and Cu(I) can be explained by proposing that one of the hydrogens of $-\text{NH}_2$ group is involved in hydrogen bonding with the neighbouring oxygen. In case of Cu(I) complex the red shift of both $\text{NH}_{2\text{sym}}$ and $\text{NH}_{2\text{asym}}$ stretching is indicative of the involvement of nitrogen of amino group in coordination which is further confirmed by the changes in $-\text{NH}_2$ wagging. All the complexes show weak absorptions in the range of 1550-1570 cm^{-1} assignable to $-\text{NH}_2$ deformation. Co(II) complex shows changes in $-\text{NH}_2$ deformation and wagging similar to those of copper complex. The spectra of all the complexes show a red shift in the C=N stretch by about 20 cm^{-1} showing that the azomethine nitrogen is involved in coordination. The new peaks observed in the lower region in the range of 480-320 cm^{-1} are evidences of M-N and M-O vibrations. The presence of coordinated water in Co(II) complex is confirmed by TGA, wherein a weight loss corresponding to one mole of water per mole of cobalt in the temperature range of 150-155° has been observed¹⁴.

From the above discussion it is interesting to note that RAH behaves in a novel manner, acting as bidentate ON donor towards Mn(II), Fe(III) and Ni(II), tridentate ONN donor with Co(II) and tetradentate ONNO donor with Cu(I), maintaining its monobasic nature in all the complexes.

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